

Synthesis and Characterisation of Nickel-, Cobalt- and Copper(II) Complexes of 1-Aroyl-4-aryl-thiosemicarbazides

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A series of complexes of the type $M(L-H)OAc$, [where $M = Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}$; $OAc = CH_3COO^-$; $L = 1$ -salicyloyl-4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide (stotsc), 1-salicyloyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl thiosemicarbazide (SCLptsc), 1-isonicotinoyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl thiosemicarbazide (inclptsc), 1-isonicotinoyl-4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide (intotsc), 1-benzoyl-4-*p*-chlorophenyl thiosemicarbazide (hclptsc) and 1-benzoyl-4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide (btotsc)] and neutral complexes of Ni^{II} of the type $Ni[L'-H]_2$ (where $L' = inclptsc, intotsc, hclptsc$ and $btotsc$) have been prepared. The nature of bonding and the possible structures of the complexes are discussed.

In the thiosemicarbazide complexes of divalent and trivalent transition metal ions it has been observed that N-N group can act as a bridging or a non-bridging moiety¹. Further, the ligation involves at least one of the N-H groups and either carboxylic C=O or phenolic OH group. In addition to the varied structural features exhibited by such complexes, they have also been found to display biological activity². In view of these interesting synthetic, structural and biochemical features, complexes of thiosemicarbazides derived from aromatic and heterocyclic acid hydrazides with acetates of Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} have been selected for the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

The 1-aryl-4-arylthiosemicarbazide complexes of Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} are amorphous in nature and are quite stable. They do not possess sharp melting points and decompose above 300°. The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The analytical data (Table 1) reveal a stoichiometry of 1 : 1 in $M(L-H)OAc$ and 1 : 2 in $Ni(L'-H)_2$. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is ascertained by the low conductivity values ($12-32 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) which is

much lower than that reported for 1 : 1 electrolytes ($65-90 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) in the same solvent³.

The ir band at $3300-3200 cm^{-1}$ (NH) of the ligands undergoes a negative shift by $30 cm^{-1}$ in the metal complexes. This shift is a consequence of drainage of electrons of terminal N atom of -NHNH- moiety to the metal ion, indicating the coordination of at least one NH group to the central metal ion⁴. In the ligands stotsc and sclptsc, the ν_{OH} band is observed at $3490-3300 cm^{-1}$. The appearance of this band at such a low frequency compared to free ν_{OH} band ($3611-3603 cm^{-1}$) in phenols may be attributed to intense hydrogen bonding of the type O-H...O in case of these two ligands. The disappearance of ν_{OH} band of stotsc and sclptsc ligands in the corresponding metal complexes reveals the deprotonation of OH group and complexation to the metal ion. Similarly, the absence of carboxylic C=O stretching vibration (observed at $1660-1630 cm^{-1}$ in case of free ligands) in the complexes supports the participation of carbonyl group in bonding to the metal. The strong band at $950-850 cm^{-1}$ (N-N) in the ligands experiences a positive shift by $15-50 cm^{-1}$ on complexation, which confirms the involvement of one or both N atom of -NHNH- group in bonding⁵. Also, S

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % . Found/(Calcd.)				λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B M
	M	S	C	H		
Ni(btotsc-H) ₂ (Yellow)	9.60 (9.32)	9.89 10.16	57.85 57.43	4.15 4.50	24.8	3.29
Ni(bclptsc-H) ₂ (Yellow)	9.03 (8.73)	9.83 9.55	50.65 50.33	3.06 3.35	22.6	3.23
Ni(intotsc-H) ₂ (Yellow)	9.84 (9.31)	10.24 10.14	53.01 53.43	4.50 4.16	24.6	3.26
Ni(inclptsc-H) ₂ (Pale yellow)	8.53 (8.76)	9.78 9.57	50.56 50.18	4.01 4.21	19.3	3.21
Ni(stotsc-H)OAc (Light green)	13.79 (14.00)	7.88 7.63	48.29 48.84	4.40 4.10	12.1	Dia.
Ni(scptsc-H)OAc (Green)	13.69 (13.38)	7.16 7.23	43.53 43.82	3.66 3.22	16.3	Dia.
Co(btotsc-H)OAc (Dark green)	14.74 (14.60)	7.31 7.93	50.15 50.75	4.15 4.26	18.8	4.54
Co(bclptsc-H)OAc (Green)	13.80 (13.91)	8.07 7.55	45.02 45.46	3.03 3.34	32.2	4.62
Co(stotsc-H)OAc (Dark brown)	13.86 (14.05)	7.53 7.62	48.99 48.81	3.85 4.10	26.3	2.73
Co(scptsc-H)OAc (Dark green)	13.78 (13.42)	6.94 7.23	43.23 43.80	2.86 3.21	16.9	2.66
Co(intotsc-H)OAc (Brown)	14.49 (14.59)	8.24 7.92	47.98 47.65	4.23 3.99	22.5	4.59
Co(inclptsc-H)OAc (Green)	14.13 (13.88)	7.86 7.53	42.94 42.52	3.44 3.09	27.6	4.16
Cu(btotsc-H)OAc (Dark brown)	15.86 (15.57)	8.03 7.84	50.56 50.18	4.01 4.21	25.3	1.92
Cu(bclptsc-H)OAc (Dark brown)	14.39 (14.85)	7.32 7.47	45.26 44.97	2.95 3.30	24.8	1.83
Cu(stotsc-H)OAc (Brown)	13.15 (13.02)	7.38 7.58	48.62 48.28	3.78 4.05	22.6	1.91
Cu(scptsc-H)OAc (Brown)	13.95 (14.33)	7.53 7.23	43.01 43.35	3.40 3.18	13.5	1.77
Cu(intotsc-H)OAc (Brown)	15.70 (15.47)	8.06 7.82	46.58 47.11	3.84 3.95	18.2	1.77
Cu(inclptsc-H)OAc (Chocolate)	15.14 (14.83)	7.84 (7.45)	41.67 42.06	2.81 3.06	14.9	1.81

atom of C=S group coordinates to the central metal as confirmed by the negative shift of 5–30 cm^{-1} in ($\nu_{\text{CS}} + \nu_{\text{CN}}$) composite mode ($\sim 750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 2–10 cm^{-1} in ν_{CS} mode ($\sim 670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with reduction in intensity in a few complexes. This trend is observed in all the complexes except those derived from stotsc and scptsc. Thus, we conclude that the potential donor sites in our complexes are (i) phenolic oxygen, (ii) carbonyl oxygen, (iii) hydrazine nitrogen and (iv) thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms. This conclusion is supported by the appearance of the characteristic bands of $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ (275 cm^{-1}) (except in the complexes of stotsc and scptsc), $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (450

cm^{-1}) and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ (415 cm^{-1}) in the far-infrared spectra of the complexes. The symmetrical bidentate coordination of the acetate ion in the complexes is indicated by two medium strong bands at ~ 1500 ($\nu_{\text{asy OCO}}$) and 1400 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{sym OCO}}$)⁶.

Magnetic susceptibility : The μ_{eff} values of the Ni^{II} complexes (3.21–3.29 B.M.) are slightly greater than the spin-only value ($\mu_s = 2.83 \text{ B.M.}$) in d^8 octahedral complexes. This is attributed to an orbital contribution to the magnetic moment possibly arising from a transfer of electron from $d_{x^2-y^2}$ to d_{xy} level. The Ni^{II} complexes of stotsc and scptsc are diamagnetic.

netic suggesting square-pyramidal environment. Similarly, Co^{II} forms low-spin complexes ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.6\text{--}2.7$ B.M.) with the latter two ligands. For the Cu^{II} complexes, the μ_{eff} values are in the range 1.76–1.92 B.M. ($\mu_s = 1.73$ B.M.) suggesting quenching of the orbital moment. However, these higher magnetic moments may also be due to a lowering of symmetry around copper(II)⁷.

In the Ni^{II} complexes, two relatively strong bands at 8600–8930 (${}^3T_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$, ν_1) and 12900–14900 cm^{-1} (${}^3T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$, ν_2) are observed. The third band (ν_3) assigned to the ${}^3T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$ transition is seen as a tail on a sharply rising band around 21500–25300 cm^{-1} . Applying weak field approximation for a crystal field of O_h symmetry various spectral parameters have been computed (Table 2). Neglecting significant contribution from Jahn-Teller distortion, the frequency of the middle peak ν_2 is calculated. The fit of the calculated and experimental frequencies to middle peak has been proposed as confirmatory evidence for the existence of O_h symmetry⁸. But the complexes under study have undergone tetragonal distortion as the calculated and observed values of ν_2 do not agree closely.

For the low-spin Co^{II} complexes, two bands are observed at ~6000 (narrow) and 18000 cm^{-1} (broad). The narrow nature of the near-ir band suggests that the transition involves non-bonding rather than the antibonding orbitals. It is possible that the ground state, ${}^2A_{1g}(e_g^4 b_{2g}^2 a_{1g})$ of the five-coordinate low-spin Co^{II} exists in a square environment. This narrow band can then be assigned to the transition from low filled orbitals to the $a_{1g}(d_{z^2})$ orbital. The other visible band is probably a transition from these orbitals to the empty $b_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2})$ σ -antibonding orbitals⁹. In the remaining Co^{II} complexes, two bands

at 9000 (ν_1) and 16600 cm^{-1} (ν_2), expected for six-coordinate octahedral complexes, are observed. The transition ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (ν_2) is absent in the present complexes. In a strong field case, this transition is not normally observed as it is formally a two-electron transition. The ratio Dq/B (1.7–1.8) found for these Co^{II} complexes confirms our prediction on the absence of ν_2 . Comparison of B (573–564 cm^{-1}) and β (0.59) values with those of other pseudo-octahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹⁰, suggests greater degree of covalency in the present cobalt(II) complexes.

The principal absorption bands expected for regular octahedral copper(II) compounds are due to ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transitions in the order of increasing energies. The latter two transitions merge and only two bands are observed for the present complexes in the region 13900–15300 and 17300–18600 cm^{-1} . In addition, a medium broad band at 23250 cm^{-1} in all the complexes is attributed to $d\pi^*$ C-T transition. Thus, the Cu^{II} complexes of btotsc, bc1ptsc, intotsc and inclptsc are regarded as six-coordinate distorted octahedral type. However, in the complexes of stotsc and sclptsc five-coordination is suggested¹⁰.

Experimental

The thiosemicarbazides were synthesised by condensing the hydrazides of salicylic, benzoic and isonicotinic acids with *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanates respectively¹¹. All reagents were of A.R. grade and used as such.

A mixture of nickel(II) acetate (0.01 mol) and btotsc (0.01 mol) separately dissolved in methanol (50 ml), was warmed on a water-bath with constant stirring for 30 min. The resulting yellowish brown solid was washed with small portions of hot methanol

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF Ni^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_1 kK	ν_2 kK	ν_3 kK	Dq cm^{-1}	B' cm^{-1}	β	ν_2 (calcd.) kK	ν_2/ν_1	Dist %	L F S E k cal mol ⁻¹
Ni(btotsc-H) ₂	8.37	14.22	21.50	837	712	0.68	13.32	1.70	7.20	28.69
Ni(bc1ptsc-H) ₂	8.33	14.04	21.73	833	719	0.69	13.34	1.68	5.22	28.56
Ni(intotsc-H) ₂	8.26	12.98	25.31	826	900	0.89	13.82	1.57	6.04	28.32
Ni(inclptsc-H) ₂	9.34	14.92	24.39	934	752	0.72	15.25	1.59	1.32	32.02

B value for free Ni^{II} ion is taken to be 1040 cm^{-1} .

and dried under vacuum over P_2O_5 . The same procedure was adopted for the synthesis of the cobalt(II) complexes. The yield varied from 55 to 60%. The copper(II) complexes were prepared by mixing hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol) and $Cu(OAc)_2 \cdot HO_2$ (0.01 mol) in ethanol. A brown precipitate of the complex separated immediately. The solution was refluxed for 2 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under vacuum over P_2O_5 (yield 40%).

The complexes were analysed for metal, sulphur, carbon and hydrogen by standard methods¹². Electrical conductivity for all complexes in DMF solution ($10^{-3} M$) were made on an Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge (cell constant 0.61). Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as the calibrant. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on an Unicam 700A spectrophotometer and reflectance spectra on a Carl-Zeiss DMR 21 spectrophotometer using optical grade MgO as the standard.

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